

Photogrammetry & Robotics Lab

Introduction to Photogrammetry

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<https://youtu.be/SyB7Wg1e62A>

The slides have been created by Cyrill Stachniss.

What is Photogrammetry?

- “photos” = light
- “gramma” = to draw
- “metron” = to measure
- Photogrammetry = measuring with light (photographs)

What is Photogrammetry?

“Estimation of the geometric and semantic properties of objects based on images or observations from similar sensors.”

What are “similar sensors”?

Two Key Problems in Photogrammetry

Estimating geometry

Estimating semantics

What Do We Measure?

- Camera localization
- Determine the location of objects
- 3D reconstruction
- Similarities & data association
- Object detection
- Semantic interpretation
- ...

Involved Disciplines

At the intersection of 4 disciplines

- Traditional photogrammetry
- Computer vision
- Machine learning
- Robotics

Photogrammetry Connections

- Developed for surveying purposes and is a part of the **geodetic sciences**
- A form of optical **remote sensing**
- Digital photogrammetry has strong connections to **image processing** and **computer vision**
- Strong links between photogrammetry and **state estimation** and **robotics**
- Uses **machine learning** approaches

Advantages (1)

- Contact-free sensing

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Why is contact-free sensing relevant?

Advantages (1)

- Contact-free sensing is important for
 - inaccessible (but visible) areas
 - sensitive material
 - hot/cold material
 - toxic material

Advantages (1)

- Contact-free sensing
- Relatively easy to acquire a large number of measurements
- Dense coverage of comparably large areas
- Flexible resolution (small but accurate or large but coarse models)
- 2D sensing and 3D sensing

Advantages (2)

- Ability to record dynamic scenes
- More than just geometry (image interpretation, inferring semantics, classification, ...)
- Data can be interpreted by humans
- Recorded images document the measuring process
- Automatic data processing
- Possibility for real-time processing

There is no free lunch!

What are the disadvantages of using cameras?

Disadvantages

- Light source is needed
- Cameras only measures intensities from certain directions
- Occlusions and visibility constraints
- One image is a projection of the 3D world onto a 2D image plane
- Other techniques may achieve a higher measurement accuracy

Cameras to Measure Directions

An image point in a camera image defines a ray to the object point

3D Perception (see Photo II)

Multiple observations from different directions allows for estimating the 3D location of points via triangulation

From the Object to the Image

The Inverted Mapping

Two Key Problems in Photogrammetry

Estimating semantics

Estimating geometry

Human Perception

Queue of human perception

object → eye → brain → interpretation

Who does most of the work, eye or brain?

Experiment

- Person, who is blind from birth on
- Camera records a scene
- Image “printed” on the persons skin using a pin for each pixel

Can this person see?

Experiment

- Person, who is blind from birth on
- Camera records a scene
- Image “printed” on the persons skin using a pin for each pixel
- Yes, the person can recognize different objects and interpret the scene

Conclusion: the brain does most of the work, so algorithms are central!

Algorithms are Central

- Estimating geometry and semantics from images requires brain power
- Algorithms are the central element and play a major role in this course
- Implementing solutions is key understanding the approaches
- Programming is a tool you must learn

Typical Sensors

Typical Sensors

- Industrial cameras

[Courtesy: Stingray, ImagingSource, UniQ] 25

Typical Sensors

- Consumer cameras

Typical Sensors

- Microsoft Ultracam (Bing Maps)

Typical Sensors

- Laser range finders

Applications

Application: Maps

[Courtesy: Google Maps] 30

Application: Maps

Application: Terrain Models

[Courtesy: NEXTMap]

Application: Environment Monitoring

Application: Environment Monitoring

Segmentation and Instances

Segmentation and Instances

Application: Aerial Mapping (1)

Application: Aerial Mapping (2)

Application: Orthophotos

[Courtesy: SIGPAC]

Application: City Mapping

[Courtesy: GeoAutomation & van Gool] 40

Application: 3D City Models

[Courtesy: Früh]

Application: 3D City Models

Application: Digital Preservation of Cultural Heritage

Application: Digital Preservation of Cultural Heritage

Image-Based 3D Reconstruction

- Seven cameras in known configuration
- Seeing points in multiple images allows for estimation 3D locations

3D Model of Cultural Heritage Site (Catacombe di Priscilla)

Application: Digital Preservation of Cultural Heritage

Catacombs of Priscilla
Access February 14, 2013 - ROBOT PATH (1th floor)

Application: Robotics

Semantics in Robotics

Visual Localization

Is this the same place?

Requires to Solve Challenging Image Matching Problems

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Robotic Cars

[Courtesy: Google] 53

What Does the Car See?

RUN

Camera-based Semantic Segmentation

LiDAR-based Semantic Segmentation

What Do We Need to Estimate?

Today's Autonomous Cars

Photogrammetry I + II

- This module (Photo I + II) is intended to provide the foundations of photogrammetry
- Key building blocks for interesting and exciting applications

Relevant Literature

Used in this course

- Förstner & Wrobel: Photogrammetric Computer Vision
- Förstner: Photogrammetrie I Skriptum
- Szeliski: Computer Vision: Algorithms and Applications. Springer, 2010
- Alpaydin: Introduction to Machine Learning, 2009
- Hartley & Zisserman: Multiple View Geometry in Computer Vision, 2004

Slide Information

- The slides have been created by Cyrill Stachniss as part of the photogrammetry and robotics courses.
- **I tried to acknowledge all people from whom I used images or videos. In case I made a mistake or missed someone, please let me know.**
- The photogrammetry material heavily relies on the very well written lecture notes by Wolfgang Förstner and the Photogrammetric Computer Vision book by Förstner & Wrobel.
- Parts of the robotics material stems from the great Probabilistic Robotics book by Thrun, Burgard and Fox.
- If you are a university lecturer, feel free to use the course material. If you adapt the course material, please make sure that you keep the acknowledgements to others and please acknowledge me as well. To satisfy my own curiosity, please send me email notice if you use my slides.